

Introduction: Conflicting Imaginaries in East Lisbon

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Marvila, Lisbon

Despite its semi-peripheral context – as a Southern European capital - Lisbon has been the stage of intensive processes of change in the last decades. Within the current juncture of global urban competition for investment attraction, in the aftermath of the sovereign debt crisis, (and subsequent austerity policies package), Lisbon has been the arena for an economic rebound mainly driven by real estate investment and touristification³. These processes, articulated with new spatialities and infrastructures of digital and platform economy businesses⁴, have been promoting abrupt and segregating transformations in formerly neglected urban districts.

This round table aims to trigger a discussion around the peculiarities of urban transition processes at the local level, bringing together an interdisciplinary group of contributors, hence different and complementary views that will enrich the debate on the on-going changes in Lisbon, more specifically in its eastern districts. We will be looking at the political dimension of those processes through the common framework of ‘conflicting imaginaries’. We resort to the notion of ‘imaginaries’ as used within the scope of social theory⁵ and on to a theoretical tradition that considers urban imaginaries as instruments of power⁶. With ‘conflicting imaginaries’ we aim to expose the often hidden contradictions and conflicting dynamics of symbolic power that emerge

³ João Seixas, *Lisboa em Metamorfose* (Lisboa: FFMS, 2021).

⁴ Franco Tomassoni and Giorgio Pirina, “Portugal: um laboratório para a Uber.” *A Produção do Mundo: problemas logísticos e sítios críticos*, edited by Andrea Pavoni and Franco Tomassoni (Lisboa: Le Monde Diplomatique/Outro Modo, 2022).

⁵ See e.g. Cornelius Castoriadis. *The Imaginary Institution of Society* (Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 1997[1975]).

⁶ Henri Lefebvre, *The Production of Space* (Wiley-Blackwell, 1992 [1974]).

along intensive processes of urban change, through notions of hegemonic and counter-hegemonic imaginaries.⁷

With this dossier we explore these dynamics in the eastern districts of Lisbon (what we would call the ‘Mouraria – Marvila axis’⁸), representative cases of a profoundly changing context. They reveal globally observed gentrification processes in once-popular historic, and post-industrial neighbourhoods, while articulating, in a local manner, material and symbolic investments that mobilise collectively produced political initiatives.⁹

Placed at the one side of the axis, on the fringes of Lisbon’s historical centre, Mouraria and Arroios are two parishes long identified by their ethnical and cultural diversity. In the beginning of the 2010’s, “low” real-estate prices appealed to young households and foreign students, simultaneously retaining old residents and migrant populations, which created an atmosphere of a cosmopolitan life¹⁰. More recently, propelled by a rhetoric that feeds on an imaginary of ‘cultural effervescence’ and ‘authenticity’ of a Southern European city, these neighbourhoods were affected by an intensive symbolic and material investment that triggered an urban land revalorisation dynamics, giving way to an atmosphere of contentious politics. Prolific social movements activity took place in what has been called the ‘comuna de Arroios’¹¹.

⁷ Andrea Gibbons, “Emergent imaginaries. Place, struggle, and survival.” *The Routledge Companion to Urban Imaginaries*, edited by Christoph Lindner and Miriam Meissner (London & NY: Routledge, 2018), 387-406.

⁸ It is a symbolic, rather than a geographic, axis formed by ‘peripheral’ areas that, although located between the central and eastern parts of the city, draw a semicircle that joins the Mouraria neighbourhood to the eastern area of Lisbon, Beato-Marvila, crossing the parish of Arroios, through Avenida Almirante Reis. (This reading is informed by Simone Tulumello, “The “Souths” of the “West”. Southern Critique and Comparative Housing Studies in Southern Europe and USA.” *Housing Studies* 37, no. 6 (2022): 975-96.)

⁹ Roberto Falanga and Mafalda Nunes, “Tackling urban disparities through participatory culture-led urban regeneration. Insights from Lisbon”, *Land Use Policy*, 108, 105478, (2021).

¹⁰ See Simone Tulumello, “Reconsidering Neoliberal Urban Planning in Times of Crisis: Urban Regeneration Policy in a “Dense” Space in Lisbon.” *Urban Geography* 37, no. 1 (2016): 117-40.

¹¹ Marco Allegra and Claudio Carbone, “Urban transformation, housing activism and social space during the Covid19 pandemic. Research notes on the bairro of Arroios.” *Partecipazione e CONflitto* (under review).

Martim Moniz e Mouraria, Lisbon

At the other side of the axis, Marvila and Beato parishes are strongly heterogeneous districts, with agricultural remnants, crossed by railways, and subject to industrialisation from the 19th century onwards. Nowadays, in the riverfront, we find warehouses either empty or in rehabilitation, old industrial structures and houses of impoverished workers (“vilas”, “pátios” and old buildings). In the inner side of the neighbourhood, behind the two railway lines, we find social housing projects with few public facilities (e.g. schools, parks, library), but also vacant and abandoned spaces¹². These were longtime-stigmatised neighbourhoods, throughout a post-industrial deflating process that has gradually been targeted by urban regeneration projects. From small cultural-led, locally embedded, and participatory processes (in the inner side of the neighbourhoods), to more recently created tech-hubs’ infrastructures and high-cost real estate investments (on the riverfront), the changing and contradictory processes of these boroughs were triggered by a global creative-innovative city imaginary, aiming to boost Lisbon’s entrepreneurial and technological ecosystem¹³.

¹² Margarida Silva, “History and Stories of Marvila and Beato”, Research Note, *ROCK Project*, ICS – ULisboa, 29pp, (2020).

¹³ Joel Scalzotto, “Smart-Up Urbanism: Critical Reflections on a Hub, Urban Regeneration & Smart Cultural Imaginaries in Lisbon”, Position Paper, *ROCK Project*. ICS - ULisboa. 20 p, (2019).

Beato Creative Hub, Beato, Lisbon

The arrival of the Web Summit in 2016 is the touchstone that eventually established the link between the city and the so-called digital economy's new agents: digital nomads, creative classes, techies or "city users"¹⁴.

This whole context of local dynamics' exposure to global economic competitiveness has both exponentially accelerated the pace of urban transformation and the intensity of urban conflict. If, on the one hand, there is a regeneration and real-estate market boom, catalysed by mass touristification and ephemeral ways of urban life – associated, for instance, with the digital economy –; on the other hand, we notice the intensification of struggles over the right to the city, as well as a rearrangement of collective forms of public space production and re-signification.

Presented as a desirable destination, Lisbon is nowadays trying to break free from that charming decadent city portrayal in Alain Tanner's movie 'In the White City' (1983)¹⁵. Longtime anticipated, and permanently postponed, socio-technical imaginaries¹⁶ are now mobilised to support

¹⁴ João Seixas, op. cit.

¹⁵ Allan Tanner (Director), *In the White City* [Film], P. Branco, A. Tanner & A. Vaz Silva (Producers) (1983). Suggested readings on the subject: Andrea Pavoni, "Lisbon in a Phantom Limb," *Desired Landscapes. A magazine reading into cities 4* (2021): 102-13; and Mariana Liz, "Lisbon on Film, 1980–2020: Locating Europe," in *The Routledge Companion to European Cinema*, ed. Gábor Gergely and Susan Hayward (Routledge, 2021), 385-393.

¹⁶ See Sheila Jasanoff, "Imagined and Invented Worlds." *Dreamscapes of Modernity: Sociotechnical Imaginaries and the Fabrication of Power*, edited by Sheila Jasanoff and Sang-Hyun Kim (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2015).

and legitimise investment attraction strategies, such as tax and visa advantages for foreign investors and entrepreneurs - ‘state exception’¹⁷ measures to swiftly allow the advancement of projects longtime in the drawer.

Researchers and activists have been emphasizing controversial state strategies (of action and omission), concerning regeneration processes taking place in these districts, in their material and immaterial heritage. We expect to uncover alternative narratives, virtual (radical) and emergent imaginaries (activated by existing collectives and social movements) that contribute to the on-going conflict dynamics, in a critical and rather concrete¹⁸ approach to hegemonic narratives.

To spark the discussion we propose the following questions:

- How have global urban imaginaries - such as green, creative, innovative, smart cities - been shaping local policies of urban development?

- Considering these global imaginaries of urban change, what are the specificities of the Lisbon case as a Southern European capital, and more specifically in its eastern districts (the Mouraria – Marvila axis)?

- How do ‘conflicting imaginaries’ allow clarifying existing contradictions and struggle dynamics of each of these neighbourhoods undergoing complex processes of change?

- How do longtime desired and postponed futures for the East side of the city still haunt present policies and investments, as well as resulting contradictions and conflicts?

- What has been the role of social movements and grassroots initiatives in providing resistance networks and counter-hegemonic imaginaries at the local level?

- Do participatory processes and/or informal, self-organised initiatives contribute to mitigate the gentrification, forced displacement, and social exclusion generated by top-down urban regeneration policies? How so?

The round table contributors will reflect on the above questions through a range of perspectives. Arguing on the specificity of urban change’s processes in this area of the city, if compared to the areas situated North and West of the historical center, Simone Tulumello explores the conflicting dynamics that encompasses Mouraria’s marginal, multicultural and cosmopolitan imaginaries with initiatives bent on branding of Lisbon as a “global city” with its extractive forms of urban capitalism.

Marco Allegra and Claudio Carbone emphasise the atmosphere of contentious politics going on in the last decade in Arroios, where counter-hegemonic strategies expose and compete with local policies inspired by globally dominant imaginaries that prefigure and/or colonise urban futures.

Roberto Falanga and Mafalda Corrêa Nunes focus on conflicting imaginaries on the inner side of Marvila, where vacant areas have been the stage for a fundamental dispute over the production of public space between local communities (living in social or cooperative-owned housing), and public authorities’ projects of urban regeneration.

¹⁷ Giorgio Agamben, *State of Exception* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2004).

¹⁸ Inspired by Ernst Bloch’s ‘concrete utopia’: ‘Concrete utopia can be understood both as latency and as tendency... It refers forward to the emergent future... [It is] a praxis-oriented category’, see Ruth Levitas, “Educated hope: Ernst Bloch on abstract and concrete utopia.” *Utopian Studies* 1, no. 2 (1990): 18.

Andrea Pavoni reflects on the unfolding of the socio-technical imaginary of urbanisation and the particular forms it takes in Lisbon's eastern riverfront. The author examines the hegemonic discursive strategies, the dominant imaginaries and their representations, with the resulting contradictions and conflicts.

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Tags: gentrification, globalization, Lisbon, touristification, urban conflict, urban imaginaries, urban regeneration
